

In situ strain sensing during the manufacture of fibre reinforced composites using optical fibres

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Presentation outline

- Structural health monitoring of composites
- Defect introduction during composite manufacture
- Global-local strain measurement concept
- Experimental case studies:
 - 1) Braiding process monitoring
 - 2) Resin infusion monitoring
 - 3) Curing process monitoring
- Concluding remarks

[Minakuchi et al., Compos. Part A, 42 (2011) 669-676]

The need for structural health monitoring

Magma's single leg offset riser (SLOF) [1]

Damage mechanisms in composite materials [3]

Magma m-pipe [2]

Heidrun High Pressure Drilling Riser [4]

[1] <https://www.magma-global.com/risers/magma-riser/>

[2] <https://www.victrex.com/en/news/2017/01/magma-victrex-partnership>

[3] Chandarana et al., Appl. Comp. Mats. (2016)

[4] <http://pangaeadrillingtech.com/composite-drilling-risers>

Defect introduction during manufacture

Fibres

+

Polymer

=

Composite

Vacuum resin infusion process

[Goren & Atas, Arch. Mater. Sci. Eng. 34 (2008) 117–120]

Possible defects:

- Voids
- Dry regions
- Resin rich areas
- Fibre misalignment
- Moisture ingress

→ ~50% of failures caused by defects [1]

Global-local strain measurement concept

- Discrete measurement points along the full length of the fibre
- Optical frequency domain reflectometry (OFDR)
- OF has a unique Rayleigh scattering profile
- Distributed strain/temperature measurement
- Resolution of $1 \mu\epsilon$ or 0.1°C

155 μm
diameter,
Polyimide
coated
optical fibre

Case study 1: Braiding process monitoring

Preforming

Resin
infusion

Curing

In-service

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Case study 1: Braiding process monitoring

- Development of strain during application of first braid layer
- Peak strains observed in locations where adhesive was applied

Preforming

Resin
infusion

Curing

In-service

Case study 2: Resin infusion monitoring

◆ Preforming ◆ Resin infusion ◆ Curing ◆ In-service

Case study 3: Curing process monitoring

Conclusions and next steps

- Advantageous during preforming versus currently available visual methods
- Strain gradients caused by infusion detected by embedded sensing
- Resin viscosity information can be extracted from strain developed during curing

Additional capabilities:

- Global-local strain monitoring of in-service components
- Combine with machine learning techniques such as ANN

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Thank you for your attention 😊

Any questions?

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